

Regulating Vehicle Access
for improved Livability

ReVeAL decision support tool process advisor

Rupprecht Consult

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	This document provides a brief description of the second part of the ReVeAL online UVAR decision support tool. The tool itself is available at www.AccessRegulationsForYourCity.eu/tool
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Work Package Title	Decision Support and Legacy
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Document history

Version	Date	Organisation	Main area of changes	Comments
V1.1	February 2022	Rupprecht	First version of characterisation of building blocks matched to characterisation of local context	-
V1.2	Spring 2022	Rupprecht and TRT	Beta version of the decision support tool	
V1.3	Autumn 2022	Rupprecht and TRT	Updates	
V1.4	2022.11.28	Rupprecht and TRT	Technical finalisation and incorporation of process guidance	

1. About the ReVeAL project

Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) are one of the most effective levers to achieve the collective goals of climate neutrality, air quality and urban liveability, and one of the inevitable pillars of the urban mobility transition. There is a need for concretely demonstrate that state-of-the-art UVAR approaches are - if planned and executed in smart ways - effective, financially viable, they make productive use of the latest technologies, fit into modern governance structures, can gain public acceptability and are compatible with legacy systems as well as with emerging mobility patterns, concepts, and business models.

ReVeAL (Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability) undertook concrete action with regards to “smarter Urban Vehicle Access Regulations” (UVAR). The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimize urban space and transport network usage through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies for the benefit of people living in these cities, to reduce emissions and noise and increase accessibility and quality of life.

The project combines desk research and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities: Bielefeld (Germany), Helmond (The Netherlands), Jerusalem (Israel), London (United Kingdom), Padova (Italy) and Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain).

Pilot cities are committed to develop, implement, test and evaluate UVAR measures in one or more of the three Measure Fields:

- Regulatory measures,
- Spatial interventions,
- Pricing aspects.

One of ReVeAL's key conceptual underpinnings is the notion of transition management, which states that changes to an entire system require holistic attention to all its components. Since the introduction of any UVAR measure impacts a city's transport system as a whole, it requires the coordinated upgrade of multiple elements of the system, which fall into four cross-cutting themes, all of which play a role in any change process:

- Governance and financing,
- Ensuring compliance,
- User needs and public acceptance,
- Complementary measures.

2. About this document

The key output of the ReVeAL project is the online UVAR decision support tool, www.AccessRegulationsForYourCity.eu/tool. The development of the tool brings together the knowledge gained throughout the project's 3½-year lifetime.

For the purpose of the project structure, the development of the ReVeAL decision support tool was divided into three deliverables:

- D5.1 Decision Support Tool – Readiness Assessment
- **D5.2 Decision Support Tool – Process Advisor**
- D5.3 Decision Support Tool – Technical Component

Early in the development of the decision support tool, it became clear that the idea of a city's "readiness" for UVAR measures in a particular measure field, as we conceived it in the proposal stage, was not enough to help cities in the implementation of UVARs. One of the lessons that emerged clearly through our project research and testing was the importance of opening up to new possibilities that can help cities to tackle existing issues and pursue their goals. For this, integration of measures was needed rather than separation. Through this, the value of developing possibilities to combine measures that span all three measure fields emerged.

- The end product of all three of these deliverables is the online decision support tool and the fact sheets and guidance it links the user to. The three submitted deliverables contain various components of the decision support tool (www.AccessRegulationsForYourCity.eu/tool) and provide a brief overview of the tool itself.

The end product of all three of these deliverables is the online decision support tool and the fact sheets and guidance it links the user to. The three submitted deliverables contain various components of the decision support tool (www.AccessRegulationsForYourCity.eu/tool) and provide a brief overview of the tool itself.

The document submitted for D5.1 contains:

1. A brief description of the development steps of the tool and the inputs and outputs
2. the Excel table showing the characterisation of ReVeAL's 33 UVAR building blocks and evaluating each of them for appropriateness against the 93 characteristics identified for a local context

This document (D5.2) contains:

1. **A brief description of the development steps of the tool and the inputs and outputs**
2. **The Excel table showing the matching of building blocks to one another**
3. **The fact sheets developed for each of the 33 ReVeAL building blocks**

Another important component of the decision support tool is the process guidance, which addresses ReVeAL's cross-cutting themes. The guidance was developed in the context of WP3 (D3.1) and is available on the ReVeAL website (<https://civitas-reveal.eu/resources-overview/publications/guidance/>). Each building block fact sheet includes links to specific relevant sections of the ReVeAL UVAR guidance.

The document submitted for D5.3 contains:

1. A brief description of the development steps of the tool and the inputs and outputs
2. The decision support tool content in its Excel format before it was translated to the online version
 - Questions to the users
 - Questions to the users with values
 - Results page

3. The development of AccessRegulationsForYourCity

AccessRegulationsForYourCity is a decision support tool to help cities that are considering putting urban vehicle access regulation (UVAR) measures in place. The tool allows the user to **self-assess** the circumstances in their city (or area) and “filter” the **33 UVAR building blocks** to suggest the ones that are likely to suit in the local context.

The tool does not have the ambition to provide a detailed assessment for every specific case. Rather, it offers a “doorway” into the wide range of UVAR measures and processes. Using the decision support tool helps you identify new options and to expand local knowledge, which can feed into the next steps of UVAR development in your local context. The output of the tool includes suggested UVAR building blocks, each of which is described in detail in a series of **factsheets**. It also offers links to valuable **guidance** on various aspects of the UVAR transition process.

Building block suggestions provided by the tool are based on a city’s goals, as opposed to being based on the current situation. For example, if a city currently has a low share of cycling, that does not rule out cycle lanes or cycle streets as suggested building blocks.

AccessRegulationsForYourCity was developed in two parallel actions. These were:

1. Selecting prioritised UVAR building blocks for a given location
2. Gathering detailed information on individual UVAR building blocks and pairing them

1. Selecting prioritised UVAR building blocks for a given location	
1. Characterising	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>This began with establishing a list of local level characteristics that can be used to describe various European cities. This was done by identifying relevant aspects that a decision maker would need to take into account when choosing an UVAR scheme. 15 relevant aspects were selected, combining for a total of 93 identified local level characteristics.</p>

	<p>For example, one relevant aspect identified was land use; related local level characteristics included: offices, retail, industry, mixed use excluding residential, etc. The identified relevant aspects were structured into four sections:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the scope (context, size of the city and size of the area that is to be approached) 2. the characteristics of the area 3. the mobility services already in place 4. the objectives for the area <p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>Relevant aspects were identified using the knowledge and expertise of the consortium in charge of the different measure fields, supported by input from the ReVeAL Reference Group in different phases of the project and the involvement of the six ReVeAL cities and their experiences during the implementation of their pilot activities.</p>
2. Associating building blocks to local level characteristics	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>The appropriateness of each of the 33 ReVeAL building blocks was assessed against each of the identified 93 local level characteristics.</p> <p>For example, the question was asked: “How appropriate is a permit charge in a residential area?”</p> <p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>A matrix of 93 local level characteristics and 33 buildings blocks was created, leading to more than 3,000 individual values, each rated on a scale from -5 (inappropriate combination) to 5 (very appropriate combination). Values were established using knowledge and expertise of the consortium in charge of the different measure fields and the deep analyses of 18 case studies from across Europe.</p>
3 Prioritising some aspects in the decision-making process	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>It became clear that some relevant aspects were more important than others, meaning the (in)appropriateness of building blocks to those aspects needed a heavier weighting in the decision-making process. As an example, it was found that the aspect of scope (e.g., single street, neighbourhood, city centre, entire city) needed to carry a heavier weighting than the aspect of UVAR measures that have previously been put in place in the city (e.g., parklet, LEZ, charging scheme). To address this, each of the 93 identified local level characteristics was assigned a weight.</p> <p><u>Method:</u></p>

	<p>Values from 1 to 3 were given to each local level characteristic using the knowledge and expertise of the consortium members in charge of the different measure fields, the deep analyses of 18 case studies across Europe and the results from the tests with the pilot cities. Test runs with 10 cities across Europe with different characteristics were carried out.</p>
<p>4 Translating the information into a user-friendly tool</p>	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>The 93 relevant aspects then needed to be translated into question to the user, and the local level characteristics into possible answers, i.e., the questions serve to match the relevant aspects of the city (as identified by the tool user) to those of each building block, to see which ones demonstrate the highest level of appropriateness. For example, the question: “<i>What are the main activities in the area?</i>” could be answered as “<i>mainly residential</i>”. Every possible answer has an associated weight (from 1 to 3) and corresponds to an appropriateness rating for each building block (from -5 to 5). The sum of all associated values and the application of the weights gives a final value to each building block.</p> <p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>The tool output is a list of 5-10 UVAR building blocks, sorted according to the total appropriateness score for the relevant aspects selected by the tool user given value. If the difference between the total appropriateness score of two building blocks is larger than 7, the tool cuts the list in that point. The tool guarantees a minimum of 5 results (even if the difference between them is higher than 7)</p>

<p>2. Gathering detailed information on individual UVAR building blocks and relevant processes</p>	
<p>1 characterising each building block</p>	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>It was necessary to be able to describe each of the 33 ReVeAL building blocks in detail, including how each has been implemented in other places in the past. The categories were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • guidance on timing, phasing, scaling and replication • whether time-window access is allowed (and possible options) • relevant complementary measures • enforcement options • gender and equity considerations • future considerations <p>For example, under the category “time window access”, for the building block “roadblock”, the fact sheet offers the following options:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • allowing vehicle access at particular times of day • allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends) • having no time differentiated vehicle access
	<p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>Key categories of building block-specific information were identified by the project experts based on experience as well as on the information available on the building blocks examined in the 18 detailed case studies. The options offered under each category were again, identified through previous experience and expert knowledge.</p>
<p>2. Developing a fact sheet for each building block</p>	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>A fact sheet was created for each of ReVeAL’s 33 building blocks as output for the decision support tool. Each fact sheet provides a definition of the building block, relevant building block-specific information divided into categories, a case example and links to further guidance (found on the ReVeAL website).</p>
	<p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>Together with the information gathered about the building block itself (see previous step), a case example was identified through expert knowledge of the use of UVARs in cities across Europe and beyond. Each case was looked at in detail through desk research and, in some cases, direct contact with the city in question to.</p>
<p>3. Develop relevant guidance about the UVAR process</p>	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>Together with building block-specific guidance, the tool also provides guidance of a wide range of cross-cutting aspects of UVAR planning and implementation. Links to this guidance are provided in each building block fact sheet.</p>
	<p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>The ReVeAL guidance was developed through desktop research together with expertise in the consortium and outside. Information on various types of UVARs was summarised, organised and structured within the ReVeAL framework. Links were created from each building block fact sheet to aspects of the guidance that are particularly relevant to the building block. Specific sections of the guidance were reviewed by outside experts. Input was also received from the ReVeAL cities based on their experience of implementation in their own local context.</p>

<p>4. Determining which building blocks might go together well</p>	<p><u>Description:</u></p> <p>UVAR building blocks is rarely used alone; they are generally part of a larger package. The building block fact sheets provide possible combinations of building blocks. Possible combinations were identified using two methods in parallel and comparing the outcomes.</p>
	<p><u>Method:</u></p> <p>A matrix with all possible combinations (between two building blocks) was set up. In the first process, partners with expertise in the relevant measure fields assigned each building block pairing a value from 0 to 3 (0: do not combine – 1: neutral – 2: good – 3: very good).</p> <p>In parallel, building block pairings were given values according to the quantity of combinations already existing in the 18 analysed case studies. These two matrices were put together to find the best combinations.</p> <p>It should be noted that only pairs of building blocks can be created. It was beyond the scope of the project to create complete packages of UVAR building blocks. For example, our methodology would enable us to say with reasonable confidence that building block A and building block B would work well together, that building block B and building block C would work well together and that building block C and building block A would work well together. Our methodology leads us to assume that a package made up of building blocks A, B and C would be successful, but this is not a conclusion that it allows us to draw.</p>

4. The user perspective of AccessRegulationsForYourCity

From the user perspective, AccessRegulationsForYourCity helps a city identify new options and to expand local knowledge by providing detailed information on the individual building blocks and clear guidance into the UVAR transition process. A user from a city – who knows the city and its mobility-related goals reasonably well – can respond to the 15 questions on AccessRegulationsForYourCity (the input) and he or she will receive as output:

1. A prioritised list of 5-10 UVAR building blocks
2. A fact sheet describing each building block, its characteristics and use, other building block that might be considered for the UVAR package implementation and a case example where the building blocks has been implemented
3. Direct links to process-related guidance that is particularly relevant to the given building blocks

See also Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the inputs and outputs of the ReVeAL decision support tool

A short video was created to walk the user through the process of using the tool. It can be found on the ReVeAL website. Some screen shots have been provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Screenshots of the short introductory video to AccessRegulationsForYourCity

5. Annexes

The following pages contain PDF views of:

- the Excel table showing the matching of building blocks to one another
- the fact sheets developed for each of the 33 ReVeAL building blocks

The Excel tables are, unfortunately, difficult to present in this form but the Excel files can be made available upon request by contacting Bonnie Fenton at b.fenton@rupprecht-consult.eu.

The fact sheets are also all available on the ReVeAL website at: <https://civitas-reveal.eu/about/approach/>.

PA7f	Road charges / tolls	Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)	
PA8a	Parking charge	Dynamic price (real time)	
PA8b	Parking charge	Fixed price	
PA8c	Parking charge	Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)	
PA8d	Parking charge	Workplace levy	
PA8e	Parking charge	From on-street to off-street parking	
RM9a	Regulation by emissions	EURO standard	
RM9b	Regulation by emissions	Zero-emission vehicles	
RM10a	Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions	Vehicle type	
RM10b	Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions	Dimensions	
RM11a	Regulation by trip purpose	Delivery and logistics	
RM11b	Regulation by trip purpose	Through traffic ban	
RM12a	Regulation by permit	Permit to travel	
RM12b	Regulation by permit	Parking permit	
RM12c	Regulation by permit	Planning Permit Conditions	
RM13a	Regulation by safety requirements	Vehicle Safety features	

Reallocating road space for pedestrians			Reallocating road space for cycling				Reallocating road space for public transport		Road charges / tolls												
Avenue	Pedestrian priority street or zone		Cycle lane		Cycling street		Bus or tram priority lane		Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)		Charge applied to specific points		Distance-based charge		Time-based charge		Permit charge		Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)		Dynamic pricing
	4	4	4	3	4	4	2	3	2	3	2	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	3	
6	4	6	2	6	2	1	3	3	3	2	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	3	1	2
3	3	3	2	3	2	0			3	0	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	0	
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4	3	4																			
2	3	2	2	2	2	1			3	2	2	0	2	0	2	0	2	1	2	1	2
1									3	0	2	0	3	0	3	0	2	0	3	0	
	2	0	2	0	2	0	2	0													
	3	6	2	6	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	0	3	0	3	0	2	2	3	1	
			2	6	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	0	2	0	3	0	3	1	2	1	
							3	3	3	2	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	3	1	2
							2	1	3	1	2	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	3	1	2
									3	2	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	3	1	
											0	0									2
																					2
																			2	0	2
																			2	0	2
																			2	1	2

Parking charge						Regulation by emissions		Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions				Regulation by trip purpose									
Price (real time)	Fixed price		Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)		Workplace levy		From on-street to off-street parking		EURO standard		Zero-emission vehicles		Vehicle type		Dimensions		Delivery and logistics		Through traffic ban		Permit t
	0	2	3	2	0	3	0	3	2									2	6	3	4
3						0	3											3	3	2	2
0	2	2	2	0	3	1	3	1									3	1	2	1	2
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0	2	0			2	0	3	0	2	0			3	0	3	0	2	0			
0	2	0			2	0	3	0	2	0			3	0	3	0	2	0			
1	2	2	2	0	3	1	3	1	3	3	3	3	3	1	3	1	2	1			4

Regulation by permit				Regulation by safety requirements	
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to travel	Parking permit		Planning Permit Conditions		Vehicle Safety features	
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3						
4						
2						
0						
1	2	1				
2	2	2	2	1		
0	2	0	2	0		
0	2	0				
4						
4						
4	2	2				
1	2	1				
2	2	2				
	2	2				
	2	0				
	2	0				
	2	0				
2	3	3				

spatial interventions:

Capacity restraint

This ReVeAL building block fact sheet is one of a series of 33, each describing one Urban Vehicle Access Regulation (UVAR) building block and providing an example of its use in a city. The ReVeAL building blocks can be combined with one another to create a structured UVAR package for a city. Try out the ReVeAL online tool, www.AccessRegulationsForYourCity.eu, to receive suggestions of appropriate UVAR building blocks for your city as well as guidance in their implementation.

The EU-funded research and innovation project, CIVITAS ReVeAL, aims to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations and associated policies and technologies to the standard range of urban mobility measures in cities across Europe. The project mission is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport networks use to improve urban accessibility, sustainability, and liveability.

For more information, please visit: www.civitas-reveal.eu.

Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Capacity restraint

Definition of the building block

Barrier to limit the volume of (certain types of) motor vehicles passing through (and stopping in) the designated area (e.g., bus or car trap, retractable bollards).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Physical barriers
- Road sign

Speed bumps and road narrowing
(Bristol City Council, 2015)

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- How to communicate the scheme

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Capacity restraint

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation
- Road block

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls: Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Parking charge: Workplace levy

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Road narrowing at a junction and 20mph speed limit in Bristol.
Traffic Choices, City of Bristol. (n.d.)

Example: Bristol, United Kingdom

Description

The city of Bristol has a 20mph (approx. 30 km/h) speed limit in residential areas. It started as a signage-only intervention, relying on driver adherence to the posted signs on the access points and within the limit area. Later 20mph zones were created with some forms of traffic calming including measures for capacity restraint, such as road narrowing and chicanes.

Road narrowing is done by extending the curbs at a junction entrance, with bollards placed on each side of the street. This prevents vehicle parking, makes pedestrian crossing easier but lets emergency vehicles pass without slowing down.

Chicanes require vehicles from one direction to give way to oncoming traffic (hence, the alternative name "priority narrowing") and most of them allow cyclists to bypass them. They consist of a raised curb on one side of the road and when in groups, they alternate direction priority.

These measures contribute to the objectives of Bristol's Road Safety Plan (2015-2024).

Enforcement methods

- Police officers
- Citizens' Speed Watch

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 2010. The 20mph speed limit roll out starts with 2 pilot areas
- 2012-2014. Introduction of the 20mph limit through the city
- 2019. The 20mph limit stays in place

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Recirculation of traffic

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:
Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Training and funding:

- Behaviour change programmes
- Training for children on how to cross the roads
- Funding support for safety at junctions for cyclists
- Local safety schemes

Mobility Improvements:

- Bus network
- Cycle infrastructure

Chicane with a sign of giving way to oncoming vehicles.
Traffic Choices, City of Bristol. (n.d.)

Additional information

The program called Traffic Choices launched by the City of Bristol is meant to aid local districts in selecting minor traffic schemes for their areas. A related web page describes alternatives for safer, inclusive and more sustainable mobility.

According to their figures, chicanes and road narrowing reduce accidents by 29%. Evaluations conducted by the University of Bristol indicate that on over 94% of the roads surveyed, the recorded speed has been on average less than 24mph.

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Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Definition of the building block

Road charges for a perimeter or an area are a daily charge to be paid for driving through a designated boundary and/or within the restricted area.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

Consider how you will deal with foreign-registered vehicles, if there will be a flat rate payment or a sliding scale according to the size of the vehicle, and how this could increase in subsequent phases.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)

Gender and equity

The selection of payment method(s) should be carefully considered to avoid excluding people with a low income or those without a smart phone or easy Internet access.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Financing
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Legal framework
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating parking space:

- Drop-off zone
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

Delivery and logistics

Road charges applied to a perimeter or an area are commonly combined with various spatial interventions.

Singapore is an example of a charge applied to a perimeter, and vehicle access is checked through a system of gantries (MOT, 2022)

Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Example: Electronic Road Pricing (ERP). Singapore

Description

All Singapore-registered vehicles, including goods vehicles, taxis, and buses, must install an in-vehicle unit (IU) to drive through the city. Access is checked via the system of electronic road pricing (ERP) and a network of gantries.

The electronic road pricing allows automatic payments for entering specific urban areas based on distance travelled, time of day, and vehicle type. Gantries are placed on expressways and arterial roads linking to the Singapore Central Area.

Payment methods

Automatic payment. The in-vehicle unit deducts the charges, which increase based on the number of gantries passed. Drivers pay either via a stored value card or via credit/debit card. The charges are based on time of the travel (in peak hours, charges can change every half hour) and size of the engine (larger vehicle types pay more).

Enforcement methods

Smart card and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)

Time windows

In effect daily, except Sundays and public holidays.

Phasing and upscaling

- 1975. Singapore's government implements road pricing scheme in the form of Area Licensing System, with a flat charge on all vehicles entering the Central Business District
- 1998. Electronic road pricing system is introduced with 33 gantries
- 2013. Expansion of the charging zone to a total of 71 gantries

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Options for foreign-registered cars without an IU:

- Renting a temporary detachable IU
- Paying a flat fee of \$5 each day to drive through operating ERP gantries

Options for motorcycles without an IU:
Renting a temporary detachable IU

Digital Parking Guidance System to check parking lot availability

Car sharing

Financial Incentives

Off-peak car scheme introduced to reduce peak hour traffic. Three types available: Weekend Car (WEC), Off-Peak Car (OPC) and Revised Off-Peak Car (ROPC). Car owners can save on car registration related fees and road taxes, in return for using their cars during restricted hours – mostly on weekends, public holidays and at night longer be driven in the region.

Every registered vehicle in Singapore must be equipped with a device called an in-vehicle unit (IU) to drive through the city. (LTA, 2022).

Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Electronic Road Pricing, Singapore

The map shows the position of the ERP gantries in Singapore. (Sgcarmart, 2022)

Additional information

ERP rates are determined based on traffic conditions. The optimal traffic speed range is 45 - 65 km/h on expressways and 20 - 30 km/h on arterial roads. If traffic speeds rise above the maximum thresholds, charges at that gantry will be reduced, conversely, it will be increased if traffic moves slower than the minimum threshold.

The Vehicle Quota System (VQS) fixes the number of new cars that can be bought every year. Prospective buyers must obtain a quota licence, that is a certificate allowing their vehicle purchase.

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Charge applied to specific points

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Charge applied to specific points

Definition of the building block

Road charges for specific points are applied to vehicles that travel through a given location or series of locations on the road network.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)

Gender and equity

Consider avoiding areas with schools, other educational institutions and hospitals/health clinics with this measure.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Charge applied to specific points

Example: Dart Charge, Dartford, United Kingdom

Description

The Dart Charge is a free flow charging service for road vehicles crossing the Thames River at Dartford.

Payment methods

- The charge is paid online or offline, in advance, or by midnight the day after crossing.
- Drivers can set up a pre-pay account and save up to a third of the cost on every crossing.
- With a pay-as-you-go service, drivers can register their vehicles and payment details, so they can automatically pay Dart Charge each time they use the crossing.

Enforcement methods

Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect daily from 6:00 to 22:00

Phasing and upscaling

- 2003. First collection of road user charges on the river crossing, by physical payment
- 2014. Start of the Dart Charge

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- EURO standard
- Zero emission vehicles

Complementary measures

Exemptions

Complete exemptions by vehicle type: mopeds, motorcycles, motor tricycles, quad bikes

The large red dashed circle indicates the position of the Dartford Crossing in the Greater London Area. The area covered by the 'planned extension of the ULEZ from 2021' is the actual extent of the ULEZ updated to 2022. (Barrett, Wedderburn, and Belcher, 2019).

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Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

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- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Definition of the building block

High-polluting vehicles are charged when they enter or circulate within the designated area.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

Phasing is often used to tighten regulations based on new car technologies. All planned phases of the measure should be announced at the beginning to allow users to make informed decisions about their long-term options.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

In a future where non-polluting vehicles are the norm, this type of ban will become less effective at reducing the overall volume of vehicles travelling in the area. To maintain this positive (side) effect, a charge based on emission standards would have to be adjusted over time, depending on the changes in average pollution levels of vehicles.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Financial or in-kind incentives
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e-)cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Organisational support

This can include logistical, administrative, promotional or other support provided by the city. This might include supporting alternative business models (e.g., for car parks that have no/fewer customers), facilitating changes and working on individual solutions to resolve issues.

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating parking space:
Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Widen pavement

Reallocating road space for cycling:
• Cycle lane
• Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

A road charge based on emission standards is generally combined with regulation by emissions. Alternately, such a charge can replace regulation by emission; i.e., instead of regulating (banning) 'undesirable' vehicles, these vehicles are charged a fee at the level of a fine. 'Compliant' vehicles are charged no fee.

On the right, the map of London, with the extent of the ULEZ in blue (Transport for London, 2022)

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

*Example: Ultra-low-emission zone, Greater London, United Kingdom*Description

The ultra-low-emission zone (ULEZ) is one of three different emission schemes in Greater London. The ULEZ extends beyond Central London to the North and South Circular roads. Vehicles entering the area must either meet the emission standards or pay a daily fee in advance. In some cases, the cost of the different emission schemes will be added together.

Payment methods

£12.50 if emission standard is not met.

Minimum standards are:

- Euro 3 for motorcycles, motor tricycles, and quadricycles
- Euro 4 (petrol), Euro 6 (diesel) for cars, private hire vehicles and small vans
- Euro 4 (petrol), Euro 6 (diesel) for larger vans and minibuses

Enforcement methods

Fixed and mobile cameras with automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

Until 25 October 2021, ULEZ residents and residents of certain areas next to the boundary could register for a 100% discount from the ULEZ. For vehicles not meeting the emissions standards, they paid 90% of the charge

Ultra low emission ULEZ zone sign, by Tim Sheerman-Chase, 2019. Flickr. CC BY 2.0.

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter: Recirculation of traffic

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:
Charge applied to a perimeter or an area

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Taxis
- Vehicles for people with disabilities
- Private hire vehicles (PHVs) that are designated wheelchair-accessible
- Electric vehicles or cars and vans that emit 75g/km or less of CO₂ and meet the Euro 5 emission standard for air quality.

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Bus or tram priority lane

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Speed reduction

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- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

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- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

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- Charge applied to specific points
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- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
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Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
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- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

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Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Bus or tram priority lane

Definition of the building block

Road space is converted to a lane designated for bus or tram movement, resulting in priority for public transport (therefore ensuring that traffic delays do not impact public transport circulation).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Women are significant users of public transport; bus or tram priority lanes should increase the reliability and ease of use of public transport, making it beneficial for women.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- How to communicate the scheme
- Enforcement options

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating road space for cycling:
Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

From on-street to off-street parking

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e)-cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Emergency vehicles
- Police
- Cyclists (in most cases)
- Residents reaching their homes
- Deliveries for loading and unloading in marked delivery parking spots

A separated bus lane in Rue de Rivoli, Paris (Transport Paris, 2020)

Additional information

The choice of the City of Paris of installing separated bus lanes during the summer holidays in 2001 generated some critics. After that, the planning commission started to be more inclusive of stakeholders. From 2020 the central Rue de Rivoli has a dedicated cycle lane and a separated bus lane. There are contrasting opinions on the success of the measure.

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Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Definition of the building block

Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are fixed according to the area of the city and/or time of the day.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

Phasing is often used to tighten regulations based on new car technologies. All planned phases of the measure should be announced at the beginning to allow users to make informed decisions about their long-term options.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers

Gender and equity

Consider an allocation of free parking spaces for people with disabilities

Future considerations

In a future with mostly zero or low emission vehicles, this type of charge would become less effective at reducing parking in general, as there would be fewer polluting vehicles in the city.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Financial or in-kind incentives
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

The ECO label from the Directorate General for Traffic (DGT) in Madrid (Seat, 2016, in La Vanguardia, 2021)

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

*Example: Regulated Parking Service (SER), Madrid, Spain*Description

The regulated parking service (Servicio de Estacionamiento Regulado, SER) in Madrid has established parking prices that vary depending on the area and the characteristics of the vehicle. The distinction by area is made between low-emission zones and other SER zones. Parking zones in the city are differentiated by colour, with “blue” indicating parking allowed for a maximum of four hours, and “green” unlimited parking for residents and two-hour maximum stay for non-residents.

Vehicles are required to display a sticker on the windscreen that is based on vehicle type, propulsion system, and the date of registration. The rates for the vehicles may include either discounts or bonuses, be free or involve penalties. There are fixed fees in long-stay car parks and in the parking zone next to the city hospital of La Paz. Finally, there are Park & Ride facilities at the city outskirts, most of which are free of charge.

Enforcement methods

- Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Enforcement officers

Time windows

- September–July: Monday to Friday, 9:00 – 21:00; Saturday, 9:00 – 15:00
- August: Monday to Saturday (holidays excluded), 9:00 – 15:00
- 24–31 December, 9:00 – 15:00

Phasing and upscaling

- 2016. The Directorate General for Traffic (DGT) introduces the national system of stickers
- 2019. The system becomes part of the programme “Madrid Central”
- April 2022. Extension of the parking charge area to other neighbourhoods beyond the city centre

Other building blocks put in placePricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Two-wheelers and three-wheelers
- Vehicles parked in areas reserved for their category or activity
- Taxis
- Vehicles for people with reduced mobility
- Touristic vehicles
- Public transport
- Administration staff vehicles (National, Autonomous Communities, Local and their public bodies, of which they are owners or have them under leasing or rental, during the provision of the services)
- Healthcare vehicles (Public Health System Organisms, the Spanish Red Cross, and ambulances; social services of the Madrid City Council, such as tele-assistance, laundry, food delivery and day-care centres, during the provision of their services and with clear external signalling for identification)
- Diplomatic representatives accredited in Spain, externally identified with diplomatic plate and in principle of reciprocity.

Financial incentives

Stickers and relative financial exemptions:

- B (yellow sticker), no discount
- C (green sticker), 10% discount
- ECO (blue and green sticker), 50% discount
- Zero emissions (blue sticker), free parking

Additional information

The system of Environmental Stickers is organised as follows:

B (yellow sticker)

- Petrol-driven, Euro 3 emissions level family cars and lightweight commercial vehicles.
- Diesel-driven with Euro 4 or Euro 5 family cars and lightweight commercial vehicles.
- Euro 4 or Euro 5 without regard to the type of fuel vehicles with more than eight places, goods vehicles
- Euro 2 motorcycles and mopeds

C (green sticker)

- Petrol-driven, Euro 4, 5, 6 family cars and lightweight commercial vehicles.
- Diesel-driven, Euro 6 family cars and lightweight commercial vehicles.
- Euro 6 without regard to the type of fuel vehicles with more than eight places, goods vehicles
- Euro 4 and Euro 3 motorcycles and mopeds.

ECO (blue and green sticker):

- Plug-in hybrid family cars, lightweight commercial vehicles, vehicles with more than eight seats, goods vehicles
- Motorcycles and mopeds with an HEV or PHEV category and a range of under 40 km

Zero emissions (blue sticker):

- Battery powered (BEV) vehicles,
- Electric vehicles with an extended range (REEV),
- Plug-in hybrids (PHEV) with a minimum range of 40 km or a fuel-cell vehicle.

Without environmental sticker:

- Petrol-driven family cars before Euro 3 and diesel-driven family cars before Euro 4
- Euro 1 motorcycles and mopeds

Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulated Parking Service, Madrid, Spain

On the left, Madrid Central markings on the ground indicating the entrance to its boundaries, by Diario de Madrid, 2018, November 29. CC BY-SA 4.0. Wikimedia Commons

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Cycle lane

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Cycle lane

Definition of the building block

Part of the road is converted to space fully dedicated to cyclists (or other types of micro mobility, such as (e-)scooters).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

Time differentiated access is generally not used.

Enforcement options

Physical barriers

Gender and equity

Women are generally more concerned about safety when cycling than men are. Well designed cycle lanes should help increase the feeling of safety, meaning more women are likely to cycle.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- How to communicate the scheme
- Enforcement options

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre "credits" allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Cycle lane

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Capacity restraint

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charges:

From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose:
Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

A cyclist on a section of the Wankdorf main cycle route in Bern. Stadt Bern. (n.d.)

Example: Bern, Switzerland

Description

The city of Bern has continually extended the cycle route network since 2016, in some cases through conversion of road space. Changes started with the city-led initiative Velo Offensive, for which a regular participation process was established. The Masterplan for Cycling Infrastructure, published in 2020, comprises the implementation of new cycle routes and bike stations.

Enforcement methods

No available information

Time windows

No time differentiation for access

Phasing and upscaling

2015. Start of Velo Offensive

2016:

- Opening of the first bike station next to the main station
- Opening of the main bike route from the central station to Wankdorf district (3 km)

2018:

- Start of bike rental system "Velo Bern"
- Opening of the main cycle route between Bern and Köniz
- Expansion of the Bollwerk bike station

2020:

- Masterplan for Cycling Infrastructure
- Construction of the bike path Burgernziel - Ostring - Freudenbergplatz

Access to the PostParc bike station. Stadt Bern. (n.d.).

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Road block

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus/ tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Fixed price

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Cycling:

- Bike stations and bike parking
- Bike rental

References

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Cycling street

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

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- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Cycling street

Definition of the building block

Road space is converted to a non-segregated street with right of way for cyclists, who are the priority users. Cars are guests and can be forbidden or discouraged to overtake cyclists. Cycling streets are characterised by a custom coloured surface and/or road marking at the entrances of the street.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

It is often easier to start with a single or small number of cycle streets and then replicate. Upscaling may be a good option when a first test/smaller implementation proves successful, and other streets also have potential to become cycle streets. A city with existing cycle streets may be able to replicate the measure to create more. The time scale for expansion is context dependent but is often related to a political mandate.

Time windows

Time differentiated access is generally not used.

Enforcement options

- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Women are generally more concerned about safety when cycling than men are. Well designed cycle streets should help increase the feeling of safety, meaning more women are likely to cycle. more women are likely to cycle.

Future considerations

In a future with autonomous vehicles, cars could be coded not to overtake cyclists on stretches of cycling streets. In a future with geofencing, it could be possible to set a maximum speed limit for cars on cycling streets, not allowing vehicles to exceed a defined cycling speed.

Further guidance

- How to communicate the scheme
- Enforcement options

Red coating marking an access point to the Mechelen cycling zone. "First the bike, then the car. Cycling zone" (Het Nieuwsblad, 2020)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Capacity restraint

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charges:

From on-street to off-street parking

Cycling street

Cyclists on a cycling street in Mechelen city centre. The sign on the road pavement shows a cyclist against a car on the background "Cycling street, cars as guests" (Stad Mechelen, n.d.)

Additional information

From April to June 2022, the municipality ran an experiment of vehicle sharing at the neighbourhood level. Thirty families of the Nekkerspoel district left their own cars home for 60 days, using instead the available options for shared mobility and public transport.

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Delivery and logistics

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Delivery and logistics

Definition of the building block

Access for delivery and logistics vehicles is regulated; this can be within a pedestrian area or a limited traffic zone focused on delivery or logistics. The rules or permits given can be by time window or be valid 24/7, and they can be with or without permits. They can provide more (or less) freedom for those with 'desirable behaviour' (e.g., low emissions). The regulations generally focus on the need to access (e.g., perishable goods or servicing the catering trade), on vehicle size/type, on emissions or on other requirements. The rules can be phased in by increasing the restricted times or tightening the requirements (e.g., emissions, vehicles affected).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

Ensure that complementary measures for sustainable logistics are in place from the beginning. This measure can be phased in by progressively tightening either time restrictions or permit requirements.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Smaller businesses may find it difficult to comply, so sustainable logistics alternatives such as cycle logistics or consolidation centres need to be available (e.g., to avoid the need for a new vehicle purchase).

Electric vehicle and cargo bikes operated by DB Schenker (Bloglobal, 2021)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e-)cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Organisational support

This can include logistical, administrative, promotional or other support provided by the city. This might include supporting alternative business models (e.g., for car parks that have no/fewer customers), facilitating changes and working on individual solutions to resolve issues.

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter: Road block

Reallocating parking space:
Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls: Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Future considerations

The increasing availability of zero-emission heavier delivery vehicles will make these vehicles easier to include in access regulation measures.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Exemptions
- Exemptions and permits in limited traffic zones
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options

Road charges/tolls can be an alternative method of implementing regulation by trip purpose; instead of regulating (banning) 'undesirable' vehicles, these vehicles are charged a fee at the level of a fine, and 'compliant' vehicles are charged no fee. A logistics bay/mini-hub can be a useful combination, and other spatial interventions leading to increased pedestrianisation can be applied as logistics congestion is removed.

the orange boundary marks the extent of the regulated area, in purple, the pedestrian area

Map of the regulated area in La Rochelle (Communauté d'Agglomération La Rochelle, 2019)

Other building blocks put in place

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Vehicles with a parking card for people with restricted mobility
- Health care and emergency services
- Armed forces and civil security
- Driving schools
- Removal companies
- Authorised market suppliers or those transporting frozen goods
- Fuelling vehicles
- Special vehicles
- Classic cars
- Vehicles older than 1990, used as part of a commercial activity for tourism

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Distance-based charge

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Speed reduction

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- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Distance-based charge

Definition of the building block

Distance based road charges are proportional to the distance travelled.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)

Allowing seasonal vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)
- Global navigation satellite system (GNSS)-based tolling

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Legal framework
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

The smart congestion charge SmartMove in Brussels includes a distance-based charge. The goals of the project are an 18% reduction in car trips, a 10% increase in bicycle trips and a 10% reduction in CO2 emissions (Screenshot from an explanatory video. SmartMove, 2022).

Distance-based charge

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre "credits" allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e)-cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Distance-based charge

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating parking space:
Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Widen pavement

Reallocating road space for cycling:
• Cycle lane
• Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:
From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:
• Vehicle type
• Dimensions

Costs and exemptions of the smart congestion charge SmartMove in Brussels can be checked via a mobile application (Screenshot from an explanatory video. SmartMove, 2022).

Distance-based charge

*Example: SmartMove, Brussels, Belgium*Description

Brussels plans to launch a smart congestion charge in 2022 within its SmartMove programme. This decision dates back to 2020 when the Minister for Mobility, and the departments for Environment and Taxation entrusted the switch from the taxes for possession and circulation. SmartMove applies to all passenger and delivery vehicles in the city's low emission zone (LEZ) which covers the 19 municipalities of the Brussels Capital Region. The charge is calculated based on trip distance, time of day (off peak/peak time) and engine size. Costs and exemptions can be checked via a mobile application. Compliance is checked through the same network of 191 ANPR cameras used to monitor the access to the low-emission zone.

Payment methods

- Drivers can pay on their smartphones via a mobile application for a daily basic amount, based on the vehicle's engine size and the time of day of the travel (off-peak/peak time), plus a variable kilometre charge based on the length of the journey and the time of day of travel (off-peak/peak time).
- Drivers without the mobile application on their smart phones can buy a fixed daily pass, the cost of which is calculated based on the vehicle's engine size.

Enforcement methods

Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect Monday to Friday from 7:00 to 19:00

Phasing and upscaling

- 2018. Official enactment of the LEZ by Brussels-Capital Region
- 2020. Official decision for setting up SmartMove by Brussels-Capital Region
- 2022. Expected launch of SmartMove over the course of the year

Other building blocks put in placePricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Time-based charge

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:
EURO standard

Distance-based charge

SmartMove, Brussels, Belgium

SmartMove covers all 19 municipalities of the Brussels–Capital Region but excludes the Brussels ring road and the access roads of certain Park & Ride locations (SmartMove, 2022).

Additional information

The Brussels-Capital Region is considering removing the LEZ for local Brussels drivers when adding the road charge, but this would still mean those coming from the surrounding area would be charged twice. The implementation has been delayed politically because this hasn't been clarified but the technical component (the app) is still in progress. The Brussels Regional Public Service offers a webpage that collects links and useful information about smart mobility. A Mobility Coach programme helps users navigate through the different mobility options for the region and there is a training programme for young and adult cyclists called BikeExperience.

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Drop-off zone shared mobility

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Spatial Interventions

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Drop-off zone shared mobility

Definition of the building block

Parking space is converted to a space for dropping off vehicles of shared mobility systems (e.g., micro mobility, car sharing, etc.).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

Time differentiated access is generally not used.

Enforcement options

- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Be aware of the needs of people with disabilities. Individual special arrangements may be needed.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- How to communicate the scheme
- Fairness and equity

Complementary measures

Organisational support

A city can support which shared mobility systems are implemented (and in which way; uniformity, infrastructure, ...) and they can support the dialogue between stakeholders (e.g., citizens, companies, providers, etc.).

Drop-off zone shared mobility

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls: Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Parking charges:

- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

A mobility point in Bremen connected to public transport (Karbaumer, 2018)

One small mobility point in a residential area (Karbaumer, 2018)

Example: Mobil.Punkt, Bremen, Germany

Description

The city of Bremen was one of the first European cities to set up a car sharing scheme. Some existing on-street parking spaces in the city have been converted into mobility points. They differ in size, being bigger in the city centre (mobil.punkte) and smaller in the residential areas (mobil.punktchen).

Mobility points are indicated by a signpost, are equipped with bike racks and are defined by an extended kerb to prevent illegal parking and to ease emergency vehicle access. There are currently 130 car sharing stations across the entire urban area of Bremen, of which 45 are on-street mobil.punkt stations.

The goal of the city is to deeply embed car sharing in the overall mobility and spatial planning strategy so that there are stations every 300 metres, for example by integrating it in new area developments.

Enforcement methods

No information available

Time windows

No time differentiation for access

Phasing and upscaling

- 1990. First car sharing initiative, 3 cars and 28 users
- 2003. Implementation of the first two mobil.punkte on public space
- 2009. Car sharing action plan sets the target of 20K car sharing users by 2020
- 2013. Addition of first small mobility points (mobil.punktchen) in residential areas
- 2022. There are currently 45 mobil.punkte and mobil.punktchen part of the entire car-sharing offer, which consists of 130 stations from different operators.

A mobil.punkt with Park and Bike (Karbaumer, 2018)

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Fixed price

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Connection of mobil.punkt with public transport

Introduction of Park and Bike

Additional information

The city is oriented to establish quality standards/certification for car sharing operators wishing to receive support from the local authority. A federal car sharing act (CsgG) came into force in Germany on 1 September 2017, that allows car sharing cars to be parked on public space

References

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Dynamic price (real time)

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- Road block
- Capacity restraint

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- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Dynamic price (real time)

Definition of the building block

Pricing of parking spaces is updated periodically during the day to match demand levels. This is done to ensure a better balance of available spaces between zones that are usually in high demand and zones that are usually empty.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers (if off-street)

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), it would be possible to more easily communicate these dynamic prices directly to the specific user, thereby making the pricing more transparent.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Transparency
- Enforcement options

Dynamic price (real time)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Parking meters in San Francisco, by Panchenks. Flickr. in Brooks, 2015

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Permanent residents can buy a permit that exempts from the posted time limit
- New or short-term residents and visitors can buy either one-day permits (up to 20) or weekly permits (32 cumulative weeks maximum)
- Business owners can buy a residential permit that exempts from the posted time limit. Businesses may obtain one parking permit for a personal vehicle per postal address and up to three permits for delivery vehicles with commercial license plates.

Additional information

Once a month, the San Francisco Municipal Transportation Agency adjusts pricing on metered on-street and city owned garage spaces to encourage parking in underused blocks and garages. In busy areas, rates increase until at least one space is available most of the time, whereas rates in less busy areas are decreased until most of the empty spaces fill up or until rates bottom out at as little as 25 cents per hour.

Recorded benefits of the pilot were:

- Over 35% increase of sales tax revenues for local businesses compared to less than 20% in the other parts of the city.
- 4% reduction of average rates at parking meters

- 12% reduction of average rates at city-owned garages
- 43% decrease in parking search time
- 30% decrease in daily vehicle miles travelled

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EURO standard

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge: Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Road charges/tolls can be an alternative method of implementing regulation by emissions; instead of regulating (banning) 'undesirable' vehicles, these vehicles are charged a fee at the level of a fine, and 'compliant' vehicles are charged no fee. A parking charge can be one of the phases of this measure or a linked measure.

Future considerations

Regulating by emission is a tool to push the change towards lower emissions. As EU emission standards tighten, the differential improvement may be less (depending on the real world emissions of newer vehicles). Putting in place tight emissions standards (e.g., Euro 6/VI) can currently also cause a reduction in overall traffic; this effect will lessen when more low-emitting vehicles are on the road. Additional measures may be needed to maintain this traffic-reducing effect.

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Regulation by trip purpose:
Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Exemptions
- Financial or in-kind incentives
- Enforcement options
- Legal framework
- Managing permits (and exemptions)

Example: Stuttgart, Germany

Description

The city of Stuttgart has a single low-emission zone covering the entire urban area, where only vehicles displaying an appropriate sticker are allowed. In some areas of the city, there is a diesel ban that prevents diesel passenger cars from driving or parking.

Enforcement methods

Law enforcement officers

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 2005. State of Baden-Württemberg passes its first clean air plan
- 2008. Introduction of the low-emission zone
- 2018-2019. Particulate matter alarm in place based on predictions on conditions from the German Weather Service
- 2019. Introduction of a diesel traffic ban for Euro 4
- 2020. Update of the diesel traffic ban to include Euro 5

Other building blocks put in place

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Regulation by trip purpose: Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

On the right, the road sign for the German Low Emission Zone. From *Umweltzone Neu-Ulm*, by Kereul, 2018, April 22. Wikimedia Commons. CC BY-SA 4.0

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Two- and three-wheeled motor vehicles
- Mobile machines and equipment, work machines, agriculture and forestry tractors/towing machines
- Emergency vehicles
- Vehicles of people with limited mobility
- Classic cars
- Vehicles for which special rights can be claimed (Paragraph 35 of the German Road Traffic Regulations)
- Vehicles belonging to non-German troops from NATO non-contractual states, operating under military cooperation, and for journeys required for urgent military reasons
- Civilian vehicles being used by order of the German Federal Armed Forces, as long as this concerns undelayable journeys required to fulfil official duties for the German Federal Armed Forces

Increased mobility options

- E-scooter and pedelec sharing
- Bike sharing
- Car sharing
- More cycle paths
- More pedestrians pathways
- New tariff scheme for public transport, reduced from 52 zones to 5 ring zones for the entire Stuttgart region

Additional information

The city administration uses electric cargo bikes and electric wheel loaders, as well as electric watering vehicles. In addition, there are some pilot projects as with all-electric light trucks, all-electric sweepers and hydrogen-powered cargo bikes.

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Fixed price

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Fixed price

Definition of the building block

Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are fixed according to the area of the city and/or time of the day.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)
- Geofencing

Gender and equity

Consider an allocation of free parking spaces for people with disabilities

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), it would be possible to more easily communicate these dynamic prices directly to the specific user, thereby making the pricing more transparent.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Exemptions
- Transparency
- Enforcement options

Example: The Hague, the Netherlands

Description

Paid on-street and garage parking in The Hague is charged at a fixed rate. It can be paid online or at parking machines, and motorists must enter their license plate number so that payment can be verified. Residents can obtain a visitor's parking permit, which entitles them to a credit of parking hours per year, and their visitors park for free. Companies in areas with parking regulations are eligible for business permits on the condition that the company does not own, buy, or rent any private parking space.

The introduction of parking regulations as well as limiting the provision of parking permits are considered in those areas where (traffic) safety and quality of life are at stake due to parking pressure.

Enforcement methods

- Registration of plate number
- Scan vehicles

Time windows

Parking charging is in place:

- Monday to Saturday from 9:00 to 00:00
- Sunday from 13:00 to 00:00
- In some streets: Saturday and Sunday morning from 9:00 to 2:00.

In some streets, there is a maximum stay of 120 or 240 minutes.

Phasing and upscaling

Since 2011 the extension of paid parking has been combined with a permit system and the addition, where possible, of new parking spaces. In new development areas (such as Binckhorst and Southwest) where parking pressure is expected to grow, the municipal Executive Board may decide to introduce or expand parking regulations. Project developers will also be encouraged to include arrangements for shared mobility in their plans.

Paid on-street parking (Gemeente Den Haag, 2021).

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating parking space: Parklet

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:
Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Motorcycles
- Microcars for people with disabilities
- Visitors and caregivers of residents with a permit
- Visitors of companies who have a permit

Increased mobility options

- Parking facilities
- Park & Ride with connections with public transport
- Park & Ride + bike sharing and rental

The underwater automatic parking garage in The Hague (Gemeente Den Haag, 2021).

in dark blue,
the regulated areas,

dark borders mark the
boundaries of the districts

On the right, the map shows the areas in The Hague with parking regulations as of 1 March 2021 (Gemeente Den Haag, 2021).

Additional information

Motorists entering the city can choose to follow one of four parking routes leading from the city ring road to the closest parking garage(s).

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From on-street to off-street parking

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

From on-street to off-street parking

Definition of the building block

Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are higher on-street than in parking infrastructure facilities to gradually reduce the presence of cars in the city streets and thereby improve the quality of public spaces (e.g., free/cheaper Park & Ride facilities).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

The availability of on-street parking is gradually reduced on an ongoing basis.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), it would be possible to more easily communicate available parking spaces directly to the specific user, encouraging the user to choose off-street parking.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Enforcement options

In Rotterdam there are different time windows for paid on-street parking (Indebuurt, 2022)

From on-street to off-street parking

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge

Example: Rotterdam, the Netherlands

Description

In 2015, Rotterdam's City Lounge strategy set a goal of reducing on-street parking. The strategy specifically focuses on fixed pricing based on parking zones, permits for residents, businesses and their visitors, and price differentiation between on- and off-street parking.

Parking is free in the park and ride facilities at the outskirts of the city, and municipal parking garage are cheaper than on-street parking. Paid parking is more expensive in the city centre than in the outer districts.

The municipality may grant a paid permit valid for one year for parking on the street. These may be public or authorised parking spaces, and in the latter only permit holders may park.

Prior to setting up regulated parking in neighbourhoods, public consultations are held.

Enforcement methods

Scan cars equipped with 12 Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR) cameras

Time windows

Times differ across zones of the city. Depending on the zone, paid parking applies:

Monday to Saturday

- from 9:00 to 18:00 or
- from 9:00 to 23:00

Sunday

- from 12:00 to 18:00 or
- from 12:00 to 23:00

Friday and Saturday, from 09:00 to 1:00
In the city centre (the regulated parking hours on Fridays and Saturdays were initially earlier and then extended to 1:00).

Blijdorp Zoo, Sundays from 9:00

Phasing and upscaling

- 1999 - 2012. Around 5,300 paid parking spaces were added per year
- 2012 - 2018. Around 750 paid parking spaces were added per year (total of 82,000 in 2018)
- 2019. 4000 paid parking spaces were added (total: 86,000) as well as approximately 300 parking spaces for permit holders (permits can be obtained by residents at a cost of €28.40/3 months).
- 2019. 1800 on-street parking spots removed of the 3000 planned by 2020

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating parking space: Parklet

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Widen pavement

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls: Permit charge

Parking charge

- Dynamic price
- Fixed price

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by permit

- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Additional information

The Municipal Executive may grant a permit for parking in spaces near parking equipment or spaces for interested parties. The license is granted for one year, with tacit renewal for one year at a time. The permit states at least name and address of the license holder and the registration number of the license holder's motor vehicle or a code; the area, the road

Complementary measures

Exemptions

In some commercial streets outside the city centre, there is a reduced fee for the first 30 minutes

Blue zone: visitors can park free of charge for a fixed maximum period, indicating the length of their stay by means of a blue disk behind the windscreen

Residents and business park tenants can buy 500 hours of parking for their visitors, who then park free of cost

section or the road sections on which the permit holder may park their motor vehicle; the period of validity of the permit.

It is prohibited to place or leave any object, other than a motor vehicle in a parking space near parking equipment and in a parking space for interested parties; the Municipal Executive may grant an exemption from this prohibition. It is prohibited to park in a parking space for interested parties without a license and contrary to the regulations attached to the permit.

The annual fee for the first permit is:

- Residents: public, €115.20; licenced space €489.60
- Companies: public, €216; licenced space €996

In 2021, Rotterdam tested a parking app for residents of a pilot borough with the aim to indicate available parking spaces and avoid parking search traffic.

A parking spot converted into a parklet (City of Rotterdam, 2016)

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Kiss and ride (K&R)

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Kiss and ride (K&R)

Definition of the building block

Parking space is converted to an area where motor vehicles can only stop for a limited time (limited to the time needed to drop off children, hospital patients, etc.).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Enforcement options

Complementary measures

Organisational support

A city can support which shared mobility systems are implemented (and in which way; uniformity, infrastructure, ...) and they can support the dialogue between stakeholders (e.g., citizens, companies, providers, etc.).

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter: Road block

The Kiss and Ride area next to Nijmegen Central Station (2022).

Example: Nijmegen, the Netherlands

Description

In Nijmegen there is a Kiss and Ride area next to the main entrance of the central railway station. The area can accommodate up to ten cars and is meant for pick-up and drop-off of passengers of the public transport network.

The K&R area is a paid parking area with a maximum 30-minute stay, the first 10 minutes being free. For longer waiting times, there is a Park & Ride facility next to the station and many options for on-street paid parking.

Plans for the renovation of the station foresee a second Kiss and Ride area on the other side of the tracks.

Enforcement methods

Parking inspectors

Time windows

No time differentiation for access

Phasing and upscaling

- 2012. Introduction of the Kiss and Ride area next to central station
- 2028. Expected completion of the central station renovation, with an additional Kiss & Ride area

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Fixed price

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Park & Ride, with discounts for train seasonal tickets holders

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Logistics bay (mini-hub)

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- **Logistics bay (mini-hub)**
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Definition of the building block

Parking space is converted to a designated parking space for logistics.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Complementary measures

Organisational support

A city can support which shared mobility systems are implemented (and in which way; uniformity, infrastructure, ...) and they can support the dialogue between stakeholders (e.g., citizens, companies, providers, etc.).

Gender and equity

Be aware of the needs of people with disabilities. Individual special arrangements may be needed.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Enforcement options
- Fairness and equity

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charges applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose:
Delivery and logistics

Example: Urban-BRE, Bremen, Germany

Description

Bremen implemented its first environmental loading point for last-mile deliveries in the city centre in 2007. The current system of micro-hubs consists of containers of roughly 3x3x4 meters placed on dedicated space which has been reallocated from car parking, and special e-cargo bikes.

Freight transport is bundled at the logistic centre outside the city centre: from there, goods are distributed to the businesses in the city centre using cargo bikes. These special cargo bikes have custom frames that facilitate loading and unloading. Each cargo bike run can move up to 180 kg, allowing for deliveries to restaurants or retailers.

Enforcement methods

No information available

Time windows

No time differentiation for access

Phasing and upscaling

- 2007. Bremen's first environmental loading spot (Umweltladepunkt) offered a reserved loading point for the city centre to vehicles meeting the standard EEV (enhanced environmental vehicle). Hand trailers were used for the last mile in the pedestrianised city centre.

2021:

- The first mini-hub was placed on the location of the former environmental loading zone in the inner city (Jakobikirchhof)
- The second mini-hub was created in an on-street parking space belonging to the city-owned parking management company, BREPARK. It is located in a neighbourhood with narrow streets close to the city centre.
- All delivery operators have their own cargo bikes for delivery.

2022:

- The second location will be increased in size to accommodate a 7.5t container.
- A third mini-hub is planned next to the freight train terminal (Güterbahnhof), in the northern part of the inner city.

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating parking space: Drop-off zone shared mobility

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

The container and the e-cargo bike used in the Urban-BRE (ULaaDS, 2021)

Additional information

The project started with a series of informal conversations with the German postal service.

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Parking permit

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Spatial Interventions

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Parking permit

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated by a permit required in order to be legally allowed to park a vehicle within the area or to drive to the parking space. Permits can be subject to a (differential) fee.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

The phases of this building block often include scaling up the size of the area affected – usually starting from the city centre. Subsequent phases could also exclude more vehicles, tighten emission restrictions or increase fees.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)

Gender and equity

Certain parking spaces can be reserved for vehicles used for transporting people with disabilities.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e-)cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Parking permit

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by trip purpose:

Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Planning permit conditions

Regulation by permit can be combined with reallocating parking space for other purposes as parking capacity is reduced.

On the left, a regulated parking area in the city centre of Stockholm, by Architects Mauritz Dahlberg and Harry Egler, 2018, January 14. CC BY-SA 4.0. Wikimedia Commons

Parking permit

*Example: Stockholm, Sweden*Description

Stockholm has a system of parking permits for residents and companies. The permit allows a driver to park in areas close to the permit owner's home and/or business and in other regulated areas. Motorists with a residential parking permit may park within their residential parking area for a lower fee and for a longer period than visitors.

The parking fees for both permit holders and visitors depend on area, times of the day, and days indicated by road signs. Residents in new developments can apply for permits in car garages, but not for on-street parking, for which they must pay the same price as visitors do.

Enforcement methods

Parking inspectors

Time windows

There are variations in time windows on Saturdays, Sunday, public holidays, and one day pre-holiday.

Phasing and upscaling

2012. City Vision 2030 specifies that on-street parking will gradually be reduced.

A project of converted on-street parking in Stockholm (Trafikkontoret, Stockholm city, 2021)

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filters: Roadblock

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Pricing Aspects

Road charge:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Permit charge

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimension

Regulation by trip purpose

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

- Park & Ride with connections with public transport
- Shared mobility

Financial incentives

Vehicles for people with disabilities pay a reduced fee

Residential parking areas in Stockholm (Stockholms Stadt, 2022)

Additional information

The vehicle must always be moved during the time it is forbidden to park and parking may not take place longer than a maximum of 7 days. Even if you paid the residential parking fee, your park is subject to space availability.

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Parklet

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Parklet

Definition of the building block

Parking space is converted to a small, public space or green space as a public amenity on or alongside a pavement.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers

Gender and equity

Parklets are particularly helpful for the elderly if combined with increased seating.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

How to communicate the scheme

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Parklet

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:
From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Parklets are often put in place in combination with a range of other spatial interventions.

A parklet in Oslo (Figg, 2021)

Example: Car-free liveability programme, Oslo, Norway

Description

The City of Oslo launched the 'Car-Free Liveability Programme' in 2017, following an initial plan to reallocate street spaces in 2015. The new programme entailed the removal of 760 on-street parking spaces in the city centre, with the exception of spaces for deliveries and parking spaces for people with disabilities. More room has been given to walking, cycling and public amenities, such as playgrounds and green areas. In 2019, the city council made a declaration on further development of the car-free liveability programme.

Enforcement methods

No information available

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 2015. Plan to reallocate street spaces
- 2017. Launch of the Car-Free Liveability Programme
- 2019. Municipality's declaration of interest for the extension of the programme

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter: Recirculation of traffic

Reallocating parking space: Logistics bay

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:

Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

Cycling: 48 kilometres of new bicycle lanes

Electric charging: New municipal charging stations for electric cars

A street open to pedestrians. From *Oslo Byliv, Kirkegata*, by Christoffer Krook, in Lundkvist, 2021

Additional information

The plans received opposition from business owners and the city trade association, who were afraid that the programme would lead to “a poorer city with less life” but opposition was overcome through their direct involvement in the planning process. As of April 2021, the car-free city programme had achieved overall success. A survey conducted by the municipality of Oslo reported that more than 50 percent of the inhabitants of Oslo see a city centre with less cars positively.

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Pedestrian priority street or zone

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Pedestrian priority street or zone

Definition of the building block

Road space is converted to a street or zone allocated and designed for pedestrians, allowing for mixed-use where pedestrians have right of way and other modes are allowed as guests, or where only resident (or other specific group) access by motor vehicle is allowed. Motor vehicle traffic is regulated through a required change in driving behaviour and/or by changes in the spatial road layout. Examples are school streets, pedestrian streets, home zones (woonerf) or play streets.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

It is often easier to start small and then upscale a pedestrian zone. Upscaling may be a good option when a first test/smaller implementation proves successful, and the surrounding also has potential for pedestrianisation. A city that already has a pedestrian area in its centre may be able to scale it up to a larger area. The time scale for expansion is context dependent, but is often related to a political mandate.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g. weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Pedestrian priority streets or zones are especially beneficial to caregivers with children but they may reduce access for people with disabilities and for the elderly. This will require complementary measures to ensure their continued access.

Future considerations

In a future with geofencing or Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA), it may be possible to limit the maximum speed of delivery or other vehicles that have access to pedestrian zones, not allowing them to exceed the speed limit.

Further guidance

- How to communicate the scheme
- Fairness and equity
- Enforcement options

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre "credits" allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

Widen pavement

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge

Parking charges:

From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose:

Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Example: City centre, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Description

The city of Ljubljana, Slovenia, started the gradual conversion of the city centre into a pedestrian area in 2007. This was one of the measures to limit motorised transport and promote sustainable mobility delineated by the city vision called "Ljubljana 2025".

In 2012 the entire old city centre was closed to traffic and the city adopted its SUMP.

In 2015, the main artery of Slovenska Street was refurbished, with car traffic banned and only buses and taxis allowed, speed limited to 30 km/h and the number of vehicle lanes reduced to allow more space for people walking and cycling.

Ljubljana's pedestrian zone has increased by 620% since 2007. Today, people walking and cycling have more than 10 hectares of dedicated surface in the city centre, resulting in less emissions and noise.

Enforcement methods

Cameras

Time windows

- Vehicle access is regulated at all times.
- Delivery vehicles have access from 6.00 to 10.00.

Phasing and upscaling

- 2007. Renovation of Wolfova Street and Prešeren Square, and pedestrianisation of the Triple Bridge
- 2011. Pedestrianisation of Kongresni Market
- 2015. Slovenska Street redesign

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Recirculation of traffic

Reallocating road space for cyclists:
Cycle lane

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

- Free shuttle service, called "Kavalir", for people with reduced mobility
- Electric tourist train
- Bike sharing

Pedestrian priority street or zone

City centre, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Additional information

The two main success factors for Ljubljana's Mobility Plan are political will and a communication strategy. The mayor implemented the car ban within his first year in office, meaning that residents and critics could experience the benefits of that and other measures before the next elections. Ljubljana twice organised European Mobility Week activities; these are designed to encourage cities to introduce sustainable transport policies.

Above, Tromostovje (Triple Bridge) after its pedestrianisation in 2007, Ljubljana (Sopotnik, 2019). Below, the shuttle called "Kavalir" is an on-demand service that transports people through the pedestrian zone. (Doric Kordic, City of Ljubljana, 2022)

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Permit charge

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Speed reduction

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- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

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Road charges / tolls:

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- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Permit charge

Definition of the building block

In an UVAR scheme based on permits (e.g., a limited-traffic zone), drivers/owners may be required to pay a fee for a vehicle-specific permit. Fees may be differentiated according to user categories (e.g., residents pay less than delivery companies), the total number of vehicles (a second or third permitted vehicle is charge more than the first) or by time window (some time slots cost less than others).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection

Gender and equity

Consider offering a fixed number of accesses at a subsidised rate or free of cost to members of low income or identified special needs groups.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs and connected vehicles, these technologies could combine to communicate the charge applicable to each individual vehicle when it enters a permit charging zone.

Further guidance

- How to communicate the scheme
- Transparency
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e-)cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Organisational support

This can include logistical, administrative, promotional or other support provided by the city. This might include supporting alternative business models (e.g., for car parks that have no/fewer customers), facilitating changes and working on individual solutions to resolve issues.

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Permit charges are used (by definition) with regulation by permit or regulation by emissions.

The limited traffic zone in Turin. From *ZTL de Turin*, by Alain Rouiller, 2014, March 28, Flickr. CC BY-SA 2.0

Example: Limited traffic zone, Turin, Italy

Description

The city of Turin launched a limited traffic zone in the city centre in 1994, regulated by permits. Vehicles can access the restricted area if in possession of either a regular circulation permit or of a retroactive exemption. The retroactive exemption can be requested after having entered the restricted area and it allows occasional transit and stops.

The central limited traffic zone has generic time windows and comprises four areas with additional regulations (the Roman Area, public transport priority lanes, the pedestrian area and Valentino public park). Access to parking garages in the limited traffic zone is always allowed; however, motorists need to fill out a form provided by the garage to get an exemption from the established penalty.

There are ten different categories of permits, identified by coloured stickers, that vary by area of residence, activity and cost. To obtain a permit, vehicles must be either EURO 3 or higher or EURO 2 or higher, fueled by LPG and/or natural gas. People with a disability pay a fixed fee of €6 for a permit which is valid for five years.

Enforcement methods

Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect Monday to Friday, from 7:30 to 10:30

Roman area LTZ:

- Parking ban and driving ban daily, from 21:00 to 7:30
- Piazza Emanuele Filiberto: parking ban and driving ban from 19:30 to 7:30
- Loading and unloading allowed from 10:30 to 16:00

Public transport priority lane:

- Parking ban and driving ban for motor vehicles and bicycles, daily from 19:00 to 8:00
- Loading and unloading allowed from 10:30 to 12:00

Pedestrian area:

- 24/7 parking ban and driving ban
- Loading and unloading allowed from 10:30 to 12:00

Valentino LTZ (public park):

- 24/7 parking ban and driving ban
- Loading and unloading allowed Monday to Friday 10:30 to 12:00 and 15:00 to 16:00 and on Saturdays from 10:30 to 12:00

Phasing and upscaling

- 1994: First municipal resolution on a limited traffic zone. The area covers 1 km² of the city centre
- 2003: Installation of seven electronic gantries
- 2004: set up of the low emission zone (called Environmental Limited Traffic Zone)
- 2006: Installation of seven electronic gantries (14)
- 2007: Installation of 10 electronic gantries (total 24)
- 2008: Installation of 10 electronic gantries (total 34)
- 2010: end of the LEZ
- 2010: installation of three electronic gantries (total 37)
- 2020: installation of two electronic gantries (total 39)
- September 2020-March 2022: pause of the LTZ during the COVID-19 pandemic
- April 2022: returned to pre-pandemic conditions

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for public transport:
Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:
From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:
Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit

On the left, one of the access points to Turin's limited traffic zone. Signage warns of the presence of ANPR cameras. (Mole 24, 2017, July 17)

Permit charge

Limited traffic zone, Turin, Italy

Red: access points
Green: Central LTZ
Dashed: Roman area LTZ
Yellow: pedestrian area
Purple: public transport priority lanes

The map on the left shows the limited traffic zone in Turin (Comune di Torino, 2022)

Additional information

From 2004 to 2010 there was also a low-emission zone in Turin; it was ultimately stopped due to lack of enforcement capacity.

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Permit to travel

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Permit to travel

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated by a permit that is granted prior to entry into the area. This can take the form of a windscreen sticker, and/or be 'virtual' through registration of the vehicle plate in a database (i.e., white list), or sometimes by letter. There can be different requirements for gaining a permit, including trip type, emissions, vehicle type, ISA, etc. Permits can be granted with or without (differential) payment.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block can be phased in by tightening the requirements to receive a permit, by increasing fees, by increasing the number of vehicles affected or by increasing the size of the area affected.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)
- Intelligent speed adaptation (ISA)
- Road sign

Gender and equity

It is worth considering exemptions or subsidies for those with special needs. This may include people with disabilities or their caregivers.

Future considerations

It may become more feasible to require Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA) in vehicles requesting a permit to travel in a restricted area. This would facilitate enforcement of such permits.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Enforcement options

Permit to travel

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:
Cycle lane

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls: Permit charge

Parking charge:

Dynamic price (real time)

A permit to travel can be used in combination with spatial interventions to use the space gained for increased liveability.

On the left, one of the access gates to the LTZ in Bologna, with signage indicating the categories of vehicles and users with a permit to travel (Comune di Bologna, 2019)

Example: Bologna, Italy

Description

The city of Bologna has had a permits regime in place since 1974, linked to the limited traffic zone. Some permits require a registration only, some a fee (permit charge). There are temporary and less temporary paid permits. All the permits apply to the central limited traffic zone and other areas of the city where additional traffic restriction measures are in force.

Enforcement methods

Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

- Central limited traffic zone: in effect daily from 7:00 to 20:00
- Areas with additional measures are enforced 24 hours/7 days

Phasing and upscaling

- 1968. First implementation of the pedestrian area in the city center
- 1974. Introduction of LTZ in two small areas of the city center 1989. The LTZ covers the entire area inside the old city walls
- 1994. First-in-the-world use of ANPR camera enforcement
- 2020. Combined LTZ / LEZ
- Between 2020 and 2025, the emissions classification of vehicles allowed into the LTZ are increasingly restricted every year.

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charge: Permit charge

Parking charge: Fixed price

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by trip purpose

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Complementary measures

Exemptions

From access limitation, payment, and registration:

- Buses
- Bicycles, mopeds (two-, three- and four-wheelers) and motorbikes (two- and three-wheelers)
- Vehicles belonging to customers of hotels, garages, car repair shops
- Vehicles in expressly authorised car sharing services

Financial incentives

Bonuses:

- Residents can convert their access and parking permits into bonuses for a public transport pass, services of taxi and car-rental with driver, car sharing and bike sharing for up to two years
- Residents over 70 can choose a ten-year public transport pass

Additional information

There are areas in the city centre where additional measures apply.

The so-called “T” area, which is named after the shape of the intersection between three of the main arterial roads in Bologna (Via Indipendenza, Via Rizzoli, and Via Ugo Bassi), becomes a fully pedestrian area each Saturday, Sunday, and holiday.

Other areas with additional measures are: the three special LTZs around the university, the intersection of Piazza San Francesco with via del Pratello, and the intersection of via delle Moline with via Capo di Lucca; the area next to the “Archiginnasio” municipal public library; the priority lanes for public transport; the two pedestrian areas in via Azzo Gardino and Piazza Aldrovandi, and the three fully pedestrian areas of Via dei Falegnami, Piazza S.Stefano, and Corte Galluzzi.

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Planning permit conditions

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e)-cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Consider combining with:

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by permit: Parking permit

Planning permit conditions

Example: Brainport Smart District (BSD), Helmond, the Netherlands

Description

Inside Brainport Smart District, parking for residents, workers and visitors of the homes and businesses located in the district is only allowed in the parking hubs. The parking regulation entails 0.2 parking spaces per house, or per 100 m² for businesses. The walking distance between the parking hubs and the residential area is preferably 250 metres and no more than 400 metres.

Enforcement methods

Implicit in the permit process

Time windows

Implicit in the permit process

Phasing and upscaling

In future only zero-emission vehicles will be allowed to access the area.

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycle street

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Fixed price

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- EURO standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimension

Regulation by trip purpose

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

- Mobility as a Service
- Mobility Hub next to the train station
- Shared mobility

Additional information

As of June 2022, most of the residential area was under development with some of the units already sold and the first residents moving in.

Above and on the left, concept pictures showing the area around the residential units without private parking spots (Brainport Smart District, 2022)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 815008.

Recirculation of traffic

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- **Recirculation of traffic**
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Recirculation of traffic

Definition of the building block

Change in the traffic circulation pattern for motor vehicles in a specific area (e.g., one way streets).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

It is important to ensure that those who will be directly affected by the changes to the traffic circulation are informed about it, as well as about the timing of the implementation.

Time windows

Time differentiated access is generally not used.

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Traffic recirculation may affect people with disabilities disproportionately if they are unable to walk or cycle. Exemptions may be an option.

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre "credits" allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Recirculation of traffic

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to a specific point
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose:
Through traffic ban

Traffic filters are often combined with the reallocation of road space for other purposes, with parking charge, with regulations by trip purpose or permit or with a through traffic ban.

Future considerations

In the future, dynamic traffic signs could enable changes in traffic circulation more flexibly, allowing for short-term changes to traffic directions, e.g., for specific events. But cities would need to be careful to communicate changes well - both to people and to navigation systems - to avoid unclear or dangerous situations.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- How to communicate the scheme
- Exemptions

A one-way road in Ghent (Het Nieuwsblad, 2021)

Example: Circulation Plan, Ghent, Belgium

Description

This city of Ghent developed a Circulation Plan, which divides the city into six districts and one big car-free area. The six districts are restricted traffic areas with a permit system and access policy. The plan changed the direction of 77 streets to force motorised traffic out to the inner-city ring road rather than travelling directly from one district to the neighbouring one.

Enforcement methods

- Access points to the car free area is indicated by road markings and signs
- Some roads are closed with bollards
- Some closed roads are monitored via Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 1993. Bicycle plan to foster a cycling culture in the city
- 1997. The Mobility Plan sets a pedestrian area in the city centre
- 2017. Circulation Plan for the inner city

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter: Roadblock

Reallocating parking space: Parklet

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:
Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions: EURO standard

Regulation by trip purpose

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Hotels located in a car-free area
- Private transport of people with reduced mobility with a parking card
- Private transport of temporarily less-mobile persons (for example, following an injury)
- Execution of works
- Property renovations
- Loading and unloading for suppliers who have to deliver in the restricted areas

Increased mobility options

Park & Ride Facilities

Additional information

The Circulation Plan officially started on Monday, 3 April 2017. The weekend of the Easter holiday was used to take advantage of a quieter traffic situation. Some streets and intersections were painted red and urban furniture was placed during the transition. Filip Watteeuw, the deputy mayor of Ghent (who received death threats before the implementation of the plan), urges not to allow loud voices and vested interests to derail the process. He advises to "Talk to people, but be persistent, and don't give in on the plan's principal benefits".

Participation (meetings, consultation, Burgerkabinet) in the design and evaluation phase led to minor adjustments in the plan.

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Road block

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- **Road block**
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Road block

Definition of the building block

Barrier (e.g., bollards, blocks, visual markings) to prevent motor vehicle access or to indicate restricted access for motor vehicles that do not have a destination in the designated area.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Physical barriers
- Road sign

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

Kiss and ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

Pedestrian priority street or zone

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to a specific point
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge: Workplace levy

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Road blocks are often combined with the reallocation of road space for other purposes, with parking charge or with regulations by trip purpose or permit.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

How to communicate the scheme

Yellow pavement, raised street level, road signage (Google Maps, 2022)

Example: Traffic Circulation Plan, Groningen, The Netherlands

Description

In Groningen, access for motor vehicles is regulated by roadblocks and time windows. Through-traffic was banned in 1977 with the Traffic Circulation Plan, when the city was split into four sections and an outer ring road was built. Car drivers are required to go out to the ring road if they want to travel from one section of the city to another. Direct access from section to section by bicycle makes the travel time and distance shorter.

Enforcement methods

Design of the road space using raised pavement and different coloured surfaces.

Time windows

- Motor vehicle access is not allowed into the city centre daily from 12:00 to 17:00.
- Zero-emission delivery vehicles may access the city centre during this time window if actual need can be demonstrated.

Phasing and upscaling

- 1977. Introduction of the Traffic Circulation Plan (Verkeerscirculatieplan)
- 1982. Final modification of the plan
- 1993. "A Better City Centre"
- 2015-2025. "Destination: city centre"
- 2022. Redesign of the Grote Markt (central square) removing bus access
- 2025. The city centre will become a zero-emission zone

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter: Recirculation of traffic

Reallocating parking space: Parklet

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:

Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by trip purpose

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

Access for 5 days:

- Towing services
- Construction, installation and repair companies
- Removal vehicles
- Delivery vehicles

Annual exemption without time limitation:

- Emission-free vehicles
- Emergency vehicles
- Care providers
- Residents
- Companies and institutions owning parking spaces in the pedestrian area
- Garbage trucks
- Road sweepers

Annual exemption with time limitation

- Security company cars
- Delivery vehicles

Increased mobility options

Walking: improving proximity, attractiveness, accessibility

Cycling:

- Improving bicycle network
- More parking facilities

Public transport:

- Additional train stations in the city
- Providing demand-responsive transport
- Making public transport more efficient

Parking:

- P&R facilities at the edge of the city
- Parking garages at the edge of the city centre
- Parking garage under the "Forum" (multi-purpose cultural centre)

Development of Mobility Hubs

Sharing:

- Cars sharing
- Bike sharing
- E-scooters sharing

Taxis: In the future, taxis and registered social support vehicles can continue to use routes that bring them close to the Grote Markt.

Traffic management systems:

- Collection and sharing of traffic data
- Real time information on traffic

Charging stations:

- Electric vehicles
- Hydrogen vehicles

Improvements in bike parking is part of Groningen's policy objectives. From *Groningen*, by Dick Aalders, 2012, December 10 Flickr. CC BY-SA 2.0

Additional information

In its 2021 Mobility Vision, the municipality of Groningen indicated future adjustments to the policy for deliveries in the city centre. By 2022, exemptions will be strengthened, access will be monitored through ANPR cameras, and the area of the delivery time window will be increased. There will be new regulations for local businesses and, starting in 2025, a zero-emission zone for city logistics will be established.

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Speed reduction

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

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Pricing Aspects

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Parking charge:

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- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

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Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Speed reduction

Definition of the building block

Variation in road design to indicate that road use is different and/or speed is limited (e.g., lane narrowing, chicanes, speed cushions).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

Time differentiated access is generally not used.

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Road sign

Gender and equity

Increased road safety and reduced noise levels are particularly beneficial to women and children. This measure can be very helpful around schools.

Future considerations

In a future with geofencing, it may be possible to control maximum vehicle speed in specific locations. Vehicle technology could be used to make it impossible for the vehicle to exceed the speed limit. Cities could thus set speed limits by street and communicate the limits to all vehicles, which would not exceed the speed limit.

Further guidance

- How to communicate the scheme
- Geofencing and Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA)

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Speed reduction

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to a specific point
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Speed reduction is often combined with the reallocation of road space for other purposes, with parking charge or with regulations by trip purpose or permit.

Area 30 is an area with speed reduction in the city centre of Vitoria-Gasteiz. In some roads the speed limit is 20 km/h (Courtesy of Municipality of Vitoria-Gasteiz, 2022)

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter

- Recirculation of traffic
- Roadblock
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space: Parklet

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cyclists:

Cycle lane

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge: Fixed price

Complementary measures

Increased mobility options

- Consolidate and improve the main network of pedestrian and cycling paths.
- Improving signalling to inform priority for cyclists and pedestrians
- Construction of high-performance segregated cycle paths to the industrial estates.
- Promote and implement Safe School Roads.

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Through traffic ban

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Through traffic ban

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated for through traffic (e.g., 'access only' road signs to prevent through traffic). This enables a scheme to focus on inclusion (e.g., of residents) or exclusion (e.g., of through traffic) of certain vehicle uses. The rules can allow access during time windows or they may be in effect 24/7. Many smaller cities and individual streets in many cities do this by use of a road sign only.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Road signs

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies. drivers and owners.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Exemptions
- Exemptions and permits in limited traffic zones
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Through traffic ban

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

Cycle lane

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission:

Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

Delivery and logistics

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

Charge applied to a specific points

A through traffic ban is often combined with traffic filters to restrict through traffic.

The EU road sign for a through traffic ban for lorries. (Green-Zones.Eu, n.d.).

Example: Cologne, Germany

Description

Since 2019, there has been a through-traffic ban for lorries in the city centre of Cologne. Heavy goods vehicles of over 7.5t maximum permitted weight as well as trucks with trailers are not permitted to transit through the city centre and the districts of Deutz and Mülheim. This measure is directly linked to the local Clean Air Plan and the national scheme of environmental stickers and low-emission zones.

Enforcement methods

Law enforcement officers

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

The ban was introduced in 2019

Other building blocks put in place

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Regulation by trip purpose: Delivery and logistics

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Lorries that meet the Euro 6 standard or better and can prove with freight documents that either the destination or the place of departure is the Niehler Port
- Emergency services
- Military vehicles

Through traffic ban

Cologne, Germany

On the left, the extent of the area regulated by the through traffic ban in Cologne (Stadt Köln, 2019)

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Time-based charge

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Time-based charge

Definition of the building block

Time-based road charges are based on the amount of time a vehicle is inside the regulated zone. When vehicles leave the zone, the system calculates the time the vehicle spent inside the boundary and computes the fee due for access (and parking).

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Radio frequency identification (RFID)
- Dedicated short-range communication (DSRC)

Gender and equity

There are no specific concerns to be aware of.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Enforcement options
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Time-based charge

Consider combining with:

Spatial Interventions

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block

Reallocating parking space:

Logistics bay (mini-hub)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport: Bus or tram priority lane

The system of Controlled Vehicle Access in Valletta, Malta, includes a time-based charge. (The Malta Independent, 2015)

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Time-based charge

*Example: Controlled Vehicular Access (CVA), Valletta, Malta*Description

The Controlled Vehicular Access (CVA) system in Valletta was launched on 1 May 2007 and the area covers the city centre.

The system calculates the duration of the visit and computes the fees for access and parking based on the tariffs issued by Transport Malta. Dedicated camera systems monitor and photograph vehicles entering and exiting the CVA boundary. For delivery vehicles a distinction applies for accessing the charging zone and the pedestrian area.

Payment methods

- Bills are sent by post, SMS, and email
- Vehicle owners can check their CVA account status by helpdesk or website.
- Payment for access and parking can be done by post, online, and bank transfer.
- Pre-payment incentives and penalties for late payment apply

Enforcement methods

Automatic number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect Monday to Friday, from 8:00 to 14:00. No fee on Saturdays and public holidays

Deliveries allowed as follows:

- Access free of cost in the charging zone
- Monday, 14:30-16:30; 18:00-9:30
- from Tuesday to Friday, 13:00-16:00; 18:00-9:30
- Saturday and Sunday, all day

Access free of cost in the pedestrian zone:

- Monday, Thursday, Saturday, 00:00-9:30; 14:30-16:30; 19:00-20:00
- Tuesday, Wednesday, Friday, 00:00-9:30; 19:00-20:00
- Sunday, 00:00-9:30

Phasing and upscaling

The CVA was launched on May 2007

Other building blocks put in place

Spatial Interventions

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:
Widen pavement

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls: Permit charge

Time-based charge

Controlled Vehicular Access (CVA), Valletta, Malta

The CVA area in Valletta, Malta, last updated March 2011 (Sadler Consultants Europe GmbH, 2022).

Additional information

The CVA system forms an integral part of the Maltese government's commitment to increase accessibility in the capital city. It found a wide consensus among residents, non-residents, and business owners.

Non-resident owners of vehicles using private garages and off-street parking areas need to register both the garage/parking area and vehicles using that space to be exempt from the CVA charges.

Residents owners of vehicles are obliged to use the garage space or the space directly in front of the garage space, and therefore may not park on-street other than in front of the garage space, except for drop-off and pick-up for not more than 10 minutes, during which the vehicle may not be left unattended.

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Vehicle dimensions

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Vehicle dimensions

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated by the physical vehicle attributes, such as weight, length, width, number of axles. The regulation (banning) of vehicles of all dimensions would result in a pedestrian zone.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

In combination with other regulatory building blocks, options include:

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access
- Triggered access restrictions (e.g., by pollution levels)

When used alone, options include:

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Road signs

Gender and equity

Consider putting in place exemptions for specially adapted vehicles, such as those for people with disabilities.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), C-ITS, IMI messaging and connected vehicles, it could become easier to direct the information on vehicle type and dimension regulations directly to the specific user. With the upcoming requirement for cities to provide digitised UVAR data, information should also increasingly be available in navigation tools, helping both vehicle drivers and owners.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Exemptions
- Enforcement options
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Vehicle dimensions

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:
Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Regulation by trip purpose:
Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Regulation by dimensions is often used in combination with other regulatory measures or with road charges/tolls. When used alone, often simply a road sign is used rather than other enforcement methods.

Regulation by dimensions is active in Milan Area C. In the picture an access point to both Area B and Area C. Bicocca district in Milan (C40 Knowledge, 2019)

Example: Area C, Milan, Italy

Description

In Milan, there is a regulation by dimension for vehicles longer than 7.5 metres entering the inner-city area delimited by the ring road (called Area C). The regulation includes a ban on access and circulation for vehicles and combination of vehicle + trailers exceeding this length and that do not comply with EURO emissions standards. Regulations by type, dimensions and regulations by emission are connected, and they have been becoming progressively stricter from 2019 to 2030.

Enforcement methods

Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

- In effect: From Monday to Friday, 7.30 to 19.30
- Not in effect on public and bank holidays
- Loading and unloading is allowed all hours except 8.00 - 10.00.

Phasing and upscaling

- 2008. Pollution charge ("Ecopass") in the inner city centre (Cerchia dei Bastioni)
- 2011. Public referendum for Area C and pilot project
- 2013. Area C was made permanent with the same geographic extent as the pilot
- until 30 September 2022. Exemption test for electric vehicles or combinations of vehicle + trailers longer than 7.5 meters.

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Permit charge

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Vehicle type

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

To be exempted from the access ban, the number plate must be communicated by midnight of the day before access, using an online procedure and a form. If applicable, the access ticket has to be paid. Exempt from access limitation:

- Public utility services
- Accessing construction sites located within the LTZ
- Money transport
- Supply of heating
- Purging of wells
- Postal services
- Roadside assistance
- Authorized operators
- Exemption test for electric vehicles or vehicle combinations longer than 7.5 meters.
- Exemption from the access ban in the time slot between 08.00 and 10.00.

Exempt from access limitation (no registration required): collective transport

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Vehicle type

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Vehicle type

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated by vehicle type, such as heavy duty, light duty, car, van, lorry, coach, minibus, special, etc. The regulation (banning) of all vehicle types would result in a pedestrian zone.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Road signs

Gender and equity

Consider putting in place exemptions for specially adapted vehicles, such as those for people with disabilities.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), C-ITS, IMI messaging and connected vehicles, it could become easier to direct the information on vehicle type and dimension regulations directly to the specific user. With the upcoming requirement for cities to provide digitised UVAR data, information should also increasingly be available in navigation tools, helping both vehicle drivers and owners.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Exemptions
- Enforcement options
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

- Regulation by permit: permit to travel

One access point to the low-emission zone, with signage differentiating by vehicle types (Municipality of Utrecht, n.d.).

Example: Utrecht, the Netherlands

Description

The city of Utrecht has a low-emission zone in the city centre that differentiates between vehicle type and dimensions. The city adopted the Dutch national scheme in 2020 and plans to move to a zero-emission zone in 2025. A proposal will be made in January 2023 whether to expand the LEZ to the ring road around the city.

Enforcement methods

Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 2020. Introduction of the national low emissions scheme
- 2021. Euro 4 diesel cars (or better) have access
- 1 January 2022. The minimum standard are: diesel lorries, public transport buses and coaches Euro 6; diesel vans and cars Euro 4; campervans > 3.5t that are built after 1 January 2001
- 2023. Possible extension of the low-emission zone to the ring road around the city
- 2025. Possible switch to a zero-emission zone

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Day exemptions for trucks/buses/vans
- 6 days/year for delivery vans
- 12 days/year for lorries
- 2-year exemption for buses with emission class 4 or 5
- Cars modified for medical reasons
- Camper vans of LEZ residents.
- Classic cars (40 years and older)
- Vehicles that are wheelchair accessible.

Special situations: Vehicle owners in financial need or in extraordinary situations

Special vehicles, registered not earlier than 2009:

- Crane truck and mobile crane
- Aerial platform
- Concrete mixer or concrete pump
- Fire truck
- Cart for retail/exhibition purposes
- City cleaning
- Army vehicles

Special vehicles, registered after 2009:

- Fairground and circus trucks
- Tractors with 4 or more axles
- Moving vans
- Trucks with a >35 tonne meters loading crane

Increased mobility options

Park & Ride outside the low-emission zone, equipped with OV-fiets racks (bike service operated by the Dutch Railways) and next to stops of bus and tram

Financial incentives

- Until June 30, 2022, residents and entrepreneurs in Utrecht and in the neighbouring municipalities could apply for a subsidy offered by the city for scrapping their vehicles of Euro 3 class or lower. The subsidy could be used for a public transport subscription, shared mobility options, a cleaner car, or an electric bicycle. The national government offers a subsidy until 31 December 2025 to entrepreneurs who switch to a new clean company car.
- Favourable tax schemes that make investing in a clean company car cheaper.

References

Gemeente Utrecht. (n.d.). *Environmental zone*. Retrieved May 26, 2022, from <https://www.utrecht.nl/wonen-en-leven/gezonde-lee-fomgeving/luchtkwaliteit/milieu-zone/>

Sadler Consultants Europe GmbH (2022). *Utrecht - Low Emissions Zone*. <https://urbanaccessregulations.eu/countries-mainmenu-147/netherlands-mainmenu-88/utrecht>

Vehicle type

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Vehicle type

Definition of the building block

Vehicle access is regulated by vehicle type, such as heavy duty, light duty, car, van, lorry, coach, minibus, special, etc. The regulation (banning) of all vehicle types would result in a pedestrian zone.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)
- Allowing seasonal vehicle access
- Having no time differentiated vehicle access

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers
- Road signs

Gender and equity

Consider putting in place exemptions for specially adapted vehicles, such as those for people with disabilities.

Future considerations

In a future with dynamic signs (and related apps), C-ITS, IMI messaging and connected vehicles, it could become easier to direct the information on vehicle type and dimension regulations directly to the specific user. With the upcoming requirement for cities to provide digitised UVAR data, information should also increasingly be available in navigation tools, helping both vehicle drivers and owners.

Further guidance

- Signage to communicate UVARs
- Exemptions
- Enforcement options
- Managing permits (and exemptions)
- Camera enforcement and privacy issues

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban
- Regulation by permit: permit to travel

One access point to the low-emission zone, with signage differentiating by vehicle types (Municipality of Utrecht, n.d.).

Example: Utrecht, the Netherlands

Description

The city of Utrecht has a low-emission zone in the city centre that differentiates between vehicle type and dimensions. The city adopted the Dutch national scheme in 2020 and plans to move to a zero-emission zone in 2025. A proposal will be made in January 2023 whether to expand the LEZ to the ring road around the city.

Enforcement methods

Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

In effect at all times

Phasing and upscaling

- 2020. Introduction of the national low emissions scheme
- 2021. Euro 4 diesel cars (or better) have access
- 1 January 2022. The minimum standard are: diesel lorries, public transport buses and coaches Euro 6; diesel vans and cars Euro 4; campervans > 3.5t that are built after 1 January 2001
- 2023. Possible extension of the low-emission zone to the ring road around the city
- 2025. Possible switch to a zero-emission zone

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:

- Fixed price
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions: Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Day exemptions for trucks/buses/vans
- 6 days/year for delivery vans
- 12 days/year for lorries
- 2-year exemption for buses with emission class 4 or 5
- Cars modified for medical reasons
- Camper vans of LEZ residents.
- Classic cars (40 years and older)
- Vehicles that are wheelchair accessible.

Special situations: Vehicle owners in financial need or in extraordinary situations

Special vehicles, registered not earlier than 2009:

- Crane truck and mobile crane
- Aerial platform
- Concrete mixer or concrete pump
- Fire truck
- Cart for retail/exhibition purposes
- City cleaning
- Army vehicles

Special vehicles, registered after 2009:

- Fairground and circus trucks
- Tractors with 4 or more axles
- Moving vans
- Trucks with a >35 tonne meters loading crane

Increased mobility options

Park & Ride outside the low-emission zone, equipped with OV-fiets racks (bike service operated by the Dutch Railways) and next to stops of bus and tram

Financial incentives

- Until June 30, 2022, residents and entrepreneurs in Utrecht and in the neighbouring municipalities could apply for a subsidy offered by the city for scrapping their vehicles of Euro 3 class or lower. The subsidy could be used for a public transport subscription, shared mobility options, a cleaner car, or an electric bicycle. The national government offers a subsidy until 31 December 2025 to entrepreneurs who switch to a new clean company car.
- Favourable tax schemes that make investing in a clean company car cheaper.

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Sadler Consultants Europe GmbH (2022). *Utrecht - Low Emissions Zone*. <https://urbanaccessregulations.eu/countries-mainmenu-147/netherlands-mainmenu-88/utrecht>

Zero-emission vehicles

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Spatial Interventions

Spatial interventions are where the road layout has been altered to favor more sustainable mobility and prevent vehicles entering. Examples of these are removing road and parking space taken for vehicles and using the space for sustainable mobility or amenities (bus lanes, logistics hubs, parklets, restaurants and more)

Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre “credits” allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Financial incentives

These will differ depending on the planned UVAR measures, but some options include:

- Financial incentives for fleet renewal, e.g., for the purchase, renting or leasing of greener vehicles (including tax exemption)
- Membership or vouchers for sustainable mobility options (e.g., public transport and shared mobility services) such as discount cards, free rides or annual passes for public transport or consolidation centres
- Monetary incentives for cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work) or for (e-)cycle or (e-)cargobike purchases
- Grants towards retrofits (e.g., diesel particulate filters, new engine or fuel conversion)
- Compensation for scrapping an old vehicle (either financial or through a voucher), often differentiated by emission standards, vehicle type or owner income.

Organisational support

This can include logistical, administrative, promotional or other support provided by the city. This might include supporting alternative business models (e.g., for car parks that have no/fewer customers), facilitating changes and working on individual solutions to resolve issues.

Consider combining with:

Pricing Aspects

Road charges/tolls:

- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge: Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Road charges/tolls can be an alternative method of implementing regulation by emissions; instead of regulating (banning) 'undesirable' vehicles, these vehicles are charged a fee at the level of a fine, and 'compliant' vehicles are charged no fee. A parking charge can be one of the phases of this measure or a linked measure.

Future considerations

Regulating by emission is a tool to push the change towards zero-emission vehicles. As there are currently relatively few zero-emission vehicles in most cities, this type of regulation may also help to reduce the overall number of vehicles in a given area. As the number of zero-emission vehicles grows, ZEVS will become easier to implement, but additional measures may be needed to maintain this traffic-reducing effect.

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Further guidance

- Communicating the aim of the scheme
- Exemptions
- Financial or in-kind incentives
- Enforcement options
- Legal framework
- Managing permits (and exemptions)

Example: Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Description

The city of Amsterdam will have a zero-emission zone by 2030. The strategy for a low-emission zone started in 2008, targeting just lorries. In 2020, a national regulation was introduced in the Netherlands to harmonise all the local LEZs. There are currently six low-emission zones in Amsterdam, which will be expanded and more strictly regulated. The city's approach is defined in its Clear Air Action Plan to meet the European standards for climate. However, Amsterdam is striving to reach the standards delineated by the World Health Organisation, which are twice as strict. The emission strategy runs parallel to the policy goal of climate neutrality and circularity in all sectors.

Enforcement methods

Automated number plate recognition (ANPR)

Time windows

No time differentiation for access
Phasing and upscaling

- 2006. Agreement to implement LEZ
- 2008. City-wide strategy for lorries
- 2020. National regulation to harmonise all the local Dutch LEZs
- 2020. Ban diesel cars with emissions standard Euro 0, 1, 2 or 3
- From 2022. Goods traffic will only be allowed within the A10 ring road with a zero-emission or emissions standard 6 diesel or petrol engine;
- From 2025. Only electric scooters and mopeds will be allowed in the built-up area of Amsterdam. Goods and delivery vehicles, taxis, public transport buses and private coaches will only be allowed inside the A10 ring road if they have zero-emission engines. The same goes for passenger and pleasure vessels and public transport ferries
- From 2030. the entire built-up area of Amsterdam will be emission-free for all forms of transport, including cars and motorbikes

in blue,
emission-free
centre (2022)
in orange,
emission-free
zone within the
A10 ring road
(2025)
in green,
emission-free
Amsterdam
(2030)

On the left, the extent of the current LEZ and the future ZEZ (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2019b)

Other building blocks put in place

Pricing Aspects

Parking charge:
From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulation by emission: EURO standard

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by permit: Permit to travel

Complementary measures

Exemptions

- Petrol fuel vehicles
- Campers
- Vehicles of more than 7.5 tons (with a permit)

Increased mobility options

- Park & Ride
- Electric car sharing

References

Gemeente Amsterdam. (n.d.). *Low emission zone for diesel vehicles only*. Retrieved June 2, 2022, from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/traffic-transport/low-emission-zone/>

Gemeente Amsterdam. (n.d.). *Parking + Travel (P+R)*. Retrieved June 2, 2022, from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/parkeren-verkeer/parkeren-reizen/>

Gemeente Amsterdam. (2019a). *Policy: Clean air*. Retrieved June 2, 2022, from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/policy/sustainability/clean-air/>

Gemeente Amsterdam. (2019b). *Clean Air Action Plan*. https://assets.amsterdam.nl/publish/pages/867636/clean_air_action_plan_1.pdf

An example of Zero-Emission logistics vehicles in the city centre of Amsterdam (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2019b)

Workplace levy

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Speed reduction

Traffic filter:

- Recirculation of traffic
- Road block
- Capacity restraint

Reallocating parking space:

- Parklet
- Drop-off zone shared mobility
- Logistics bay (mini-hub)
- Kiss & Ride (K&R)

Reallocating road space for pedestrians:

- Widen pavement
- Pedestrian priority street or zone

Reallocating road space for cycling:

- Cycle lane
- Cycling street

Reallocating road space for public transport:

- Bus or tram priority lane

Pricing Aspects

Pricing aspects are when the entry to an area or to the entirety of the city is given a price tag to encourage more sustainable transport. Pricing aspects also include the (differential) levels of penalty fees to encourage (and enforce) compliance.

Road charges / tolls:

- Charge applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)
- Charge applied to specific points
- Distance-based charge
- Time-based charge
- Permit charge
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)

Parking charge:

- Dynamic price (real time)
- Fixed price
- Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)
- Workplace levy
- From on-street to off-street parking

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory measures are those where there is a legal instrument that states who can and cannot enter an area. They could often also be called "bans" and include Zero Emission Zones, Low Emission Zones, and Limited Traffic Zones.

Regulation by emissions:

- Euro standard
- Zero-emission vehicles

Regulation by vehicle type and dimensions:

- Vehicle type
- Dimensions

Regulation by trip purpose:

- Delivery and logistics
- Through traffic ban

Regulation by permit:

- Permit to travel
- Parking permit
- Planning permit conditions

Definition of the building block

Charge on employers and educational institutions (schools, universities) for the number of parking places they provide for use by employees, students or others.

Timing, phasing, scaling and replication

This building block has no-timing related issues requiring specific attention.

Time windows

- Allowing vehicle access at particular times of day
- Allowing vehicle access on given days of the week (e.g., weekends)

Enforcement options

- Cameras with automated number plate recognition (ANPR)
- Manual enforcement through visual inspection
- Physical barriers

Gender and equity

This could be linked to public transport tickets as an incentive/reward for those who do not travel by car.

Future considerations

No specific effects are foreseen for this building block from future technologies.

Further guidance

- Complementary sustainable mobility measures
- Transparency

Complementary measures

Exemptions

The types of exemptions will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Key exemptions for police, fire department, waste collection, etc.
- User needs exemptions, e.g. for people with disabilities with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries
- Exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted or converted electric or hybrid vehicles)
- Limited numbers of purchased exemptions for entry (e.g., per day/month/year) to a specific zone
- Specified maximum amount of kilometre "credits" allocated to individuals or businesses

Increased mobility options

The types of increased mobility options will be different depending on the scheme type, but some examples are:

- Creation of mobility hubs
- Increasing/improving walking or cycling facilities
- Increasing/improving public transport
- Facilitating vehicle hire and/or car sharing
- Providing parking spaces in alternative locations (e.g., Park & Ride)

Complementary measures

Exemptions

Not contributing to the count of parking spaces:

- Occasional business visitor
- Customer vehicles
- Delivery vehicles

Free for:

- Vehicles for people with disabilities
- National health services (NHS) premises
- Emergency vehicles

Financial Incentives

Workplace Travel Grants

Business, public and voluntary sector organisations can apply for a grant of up to £25,000 for different types of workplace travel support. This may include one or a combination of the following:

Cycling and Walking

- Cycle parking and shelters, including CCTV and shelter lighting
- Shower/changing/drying facilities
- Changes to entrances and pedestrian route lighting (maintenance/running costs not included)
- Pool (electric) bikes
- Personal safety/security equipment
- e-Cargo bikes

Financial Incentives (2/2)

Public transport: workplace real-time display screens

Ultra-Low-Emission Vehicle (ULEV) support

- Electric vehicle (EV) charge points ground or wall mounted, with or without tethered cables, up to 22kw
- Charge point installation costs e.g. grid connection, ground work, concrete base and crash barriers
- Signage and bay marking related to charge point installations
- Bollards or guards to protect charge point/s from damage, e.g. reversing vehicles
- Charging cables – where charge points do not have a tethered cable.
- Receiving back office connection to the Charge point Management System, including RFID cards/access devices
- 3 year warranty (an essential requirement for all charge point installations under this scheme)
- 1 year data costs (3 years required)
- Electric car club supportive infrastructure e.g. signs, markings, bollards

Parking management: car parking infrastructure e.g. barrier controls, signage (excludes perimeter fencing around car parking areas)

Ningbo Bridge. The workplace levy has been financing the new tram infrastructure of Nottingham (Bishop, 2018)

Additional information

The official city's website states that Employers, rather than employees, are responsible for paying any WPL charge, although employers can choose to reclaim part or all of the cost of the WPL from their employees.

References

Bishop D. (2018, January 19). *How Nottingham created the UK's first workplace parking levy*. LGC Idea Exchange. <https://www.lgcplus.com/idea-exchange/how-nottingham-created-the-uks-first-workplace-parking-levy-19-01-2018/>

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